

Incwadana Yolondolozo **LWEZITYALO**

**Ukuphuhlisa izakhono zoluntu lwasekuhlaleni kwi-Agroforestry
yesiNtu kummandla wase-Amadiba eMpuma Mpondoland**

Ukuqinisekisa ukuba isityalo sikhuselekile kwaye akukho moya usala ejikeleze iingcambu, bamba umqolo omkhulu wesityalo, usebenzise izandla okanye iinyawo zakho ukutyumza umhlaba kancinci ujikeleze isityalo.

Ukuze ulinganise isangqa sesiqu kwindawo yesingxobo seengcambu (root collar), qhoboshela intambo yokulinganisa ejikeleze inxalenye yesiqu esivelayo emhlabeni. Ukuze ulinganise ukuphakama kwesityalo, qala ekungeneni kweengcambu (root collar) ukuya kwelona gqabi liphezulu (apex).

IDATHA YEMETADATA

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Igama leProjekthi: Ukuphuhlisa izakhono zoluntu lwemveli kwi-agroforestry kwiNdawo yase-Amadiba eMpuma Mpondoland.

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Imithombo yolwazi eqinisekisiweyo:

Fox, F.W., & Norwood Young, M.E. (1982). Food from the Veld: edible plants of South Africa. Delta Books, Johannesburg. ISBN 0908387326.

PlantZAfrica <http://pza.sanbi.org/>

Useful Tropical Plants <http://tropical.theferns.info/>

World Agroforestry Centre <https://apps.worldagroforestry.org/treedb/>

Iprojekthi lusebenziswano phakathi kwe-Institute of Natural Resources (INR), i-Sustaining the Wild Coast (SWC), kunye ne-Siyasisiza Trust (ST). Kolu sebeziswano, i-INR izisa ulwazi lwezenzululwazi kunye nobuchwephesha malunga neentlobo zezityalo eziphuma kwi-agroforestry yemveli, i-SWC inika amakhonkco kunye namaqonga oluntu lwemveli lwendawo, kwaye i-ST izisa ubuchule bobugcisa kwiziseko ze-agroecology ezimiswe kule ndawo.

Ukwamkelwa: Iqela leprojekthi libulela kakhulu i-Farmers Forum, amalungu e-SWC, kunye ne-ST ngokulungiselela nokulawula iindibano ze workshops kunye nokutyala, kuquka unxibelelwano, ezothutho, ukulungiselela ukutya, kunye nokulungelelanisa imizamo yoluntu. Sibulela kakhulu kuluntu lwasekuhlaleni ngokwamkela kwabo ngobubele, ukuthatha inxaxheba kwabo, kunye nokusebenza kwabo ngokufanelekileyo ekutyaleni. Sikwavuma umbulelo kwi-UNDP GEF Small Grants Programme ngenkxaso-mali yalo msebenzi.

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INTSHAYELELO

Ummandla wase-Amadiba kwiphondo laseMpuma Koloni, eMzantsi Afrika, uyindawo enobutyebi obukhulu bezilwanyana nezityalo, kwaye ugomnye wemimandla embalwa esasebenzisa iindlela zemveli zokulima. Lo mmandla ujongene nomngeni wokuhlaselwa zizityalo nezilwanyana zasemzini, ukunqanyulwa okanye ukhukhuliseko kunxweme, ukonakala nokutshiswa komhlaba, kunye nokuphulukana nelifa leenkubeko ngenxa yokufuduka kwabantu abatsha. Iprojekthi ibandakanya abahlali bamaphandle amathandathu aquka ummandla wase-Amadiba ekukhetheni, ekutyaleni, ekukhuliseni, nasekusebenziseni iintlobo zezityalo zemveli ezifanelekileyo ukuze kuphuculwe impilo-ntle yabo. Ezi zityalo ziya kuncedisana nokhuseleko lokutya kunye noqoqosho lwamakhaya ngendlela yemveliso engengawo amaplanga efana nefayibha, ukudla kwezilwanyana, amayeza, kunye nemithi yokwakha.

Iprojekthi sele ityalile izityalo ezingama-2700 ezibandakanya iintlobo ezingama-32, kumhlaba omalunga ne-125 hectares kwezi lali zintandathu, ngenjongo yokukhuthaza i-agroforestry exhathisa utshintsho lwemozulu. Kwenzekile nokuba kulandelwe indlela yokwenza imephu ngokuthatha inxaxheba yabahlali ukuze kubonwe, kuqwalaselwe, kuyilwe, kwaye kutyalwe kwiindawo ezifanelekileyo kwiilali zabo, ukwenzela ukuba zinike iinzuzo ezifana nokubonelela ngokutya, iindonga eziphilayo, imiqobo yomoya, ukomelezwa komhlaba, kunye nokugcina amanzi.

Abahlali baza kufundiswa indlela yokubeka esweni, ukwandisa okanye ukutyala, kunye nokusebenzisa izityalo ngendlela ezinzileyo ukuze bazisebenzisele bona, kwaye baza kucwangcisa namathuba oshishino asekelwe ekukhuliseni nasekuphuhliseni iimveliso ezivela kwezi zityalo kwixesha elizayo. Le projekthi iza kwakha izakhono kumalungu oluntu, kuquka abafazi kunye nolutsha, ekuqaleni nasekuyilweni kwe-agroforestry, ekukhulisweni kwezityalo, ekusebenziseni izityalo ngendlela ezinzileyo, nakwimiba yamathuba oshishino. Esi siqwenga seemanuwali sibhala iinkqubo ezisetyenziswe ekutyalweni kwezi ntlobo zezityalo, ekunakekeleni kwazo, kunye nokuqwalasela ukukhula kwazo ngexesha leenyanga ezintandathu. Sikwanika nemigaqo ngokubanzi yokusebenzisa izityalo ngendlela ezinzileyo kunye nobuchule bazo bokuphindaphindwa.

INKQUBO YOKUTYALA

A. Ukumba

1. Linganisela kwaye uphawule iindawo eziza kutyalwa, uqaphele ububanzi kunye nobunzulu bemngxuma, kunye nomgama phakathi kwazo, njengoko kubonisiwe kwiphepha lesalathiso. Shiya ubuncinane imitha enye phakathi kwezityalo eziza kukhula zibe ziintango, kwaye ngakumbi (njengoko kucetyiswe kwiphepha lesalathiso) kwizityalo ezinkulu. Sishiya iimitha ezintlanu phakathi kwemithi emikhulu enika imithunzi, iimitha ezintathu phakathi kwemithi enomthi oqinileyo nothintela okanye ovikela umoya, kunye neemitha ezimbini kwiindawo ezityalwayo ukuphepha umonakalo obangelwa yimvula okanye womoya.
2. Vula umhlaba ngokusebenzisa ifosholo, ukrobele umhlaba ongaphezulu. Hlanganisa umhlaba ongaphezulu kwindawo enye ukuze usetyenziswe kamva. Umhlaba ongaphezulu uphakathi kwe-10 ukuya kwi-20cm ubunzulu, umbala omnyama kwaye umanzi, ulandelwa ngumhlaba opholileyo oqinileyo onombala okhanyayo, onokubekwa kwindawo eyahlukileyo. Ukuba umhlaba ongaphantsi komhlaba ongaphezulu unamatye amaninzi, cinga ngokuhambisa umngxuma kwenye indawo.
3. Imingxuma ihlala inobubanzi, ubunzulu kunye nobude obulinganayo. Yenza nzulu kwaye wandise umngxuma ukuya kubunzulu obufunekayo, uqinisekise ukuba uhlala inobubanzi obulinganayo kuze kube sesiphelweni: umngxuma kufuneka ube nesimo sesikwere okanye umbhobho, hayi umngxuma onemilo ye-U okanye ye-V.

4. Gcwalisa umngxuma ogqityiweyo ngamanzi kwaye uvumele onke amanzi angene emhlabeni. Sitsibe eli nyathelo kuba bekukho imvula enkulu kwiintsuku ezidlulileyo, kwaye umhlaba wawusele umanzi kakhulu.

B. Ukumisa Isityalo

5. Khulula ngobunono isityalo kwisikhongozeli saso ngokusinyinyithekisa; injongo kukuqinisekisa ukuba umhlaba usekhona kwiimpande. Ukuba kusetyenziswa unyango lomhlaba njengomgquba, sasaza umaleko omncinci wezinto ezinjalo emazantsi omngxuma; eli nyathelo liyakhethwa okanye alinyanzelisi.
6. Thoba isityalo kumngxuma omanzi, kwaye uqinisekise ukuba kukho isithuba esaneleyo sempande zonke, kubunzulu nasebubanzini. Iimpande akufuneki zinyanzelwe, zigobe, okanye zibonakale phezu komhlaba. Lungelelanisa ubungakanani bomngxuma ukuba kuyimfuneko, ukuze iimpande zihlale kakuhle ngaphandle koxinzelelo. Iimpande kufuneka zihlale isentimitha enye ngaphantsi komhlaba. Amagqabi kunye namasebe kufuneka onke ahlale ngaphezulu komhlaba.
7. Ukuqinisekisa ukuba iimpande zihlala isentimitha enye ngaphantsi komhlaba kwaye amagqabi onke angaphezulu komhlaba, gcwalisa umngxuma kuqala ngomhlaba ongaphezulu. Ukuba kuyimfuneko, yongeza umgquba, umhlaba ongakumbi, okanye umxube wokutyala ude umngxuma ugcwale ngokupheleleyo.

C. Ukumisa Isityalo

8. Bamba isiqu esikhulu sesityalo (kunye nawo nawaphantsi amagqabi), uze usebenzise izandla okanye unyawo ukuze ucinezele ngobunono umhlaba ojikeleze isiqu sesityalo; injongo kukususa imingxuma yomoya engaphezulu ukuze iimpande zingomi.
9. Yongeza umhlaba ongakumbi ukuze ugcwalise umngxuma ukuba kuyimfuneko, kwaye uqinisekise ukuba isiqu sihlala isentimitha enye ngaphantsi komhlaba. Yenza isangqa somhlaba ojikeleze isityalo ukuze usebenze njengomsele wokugcina amanzi.
10. Nkcnkceshela isityalo ukuze ugcwalise umsele wamanzi uze uvumele amanzi angene emhlabeni. Ukuba kuyimfuneko, fakela umaleko omncinci wezinto ezomileyo ngaphakathi okanye ecaleni komsele wokugcina amanzi.

Umzobo 1: Xa utyala izityalo, shiya isithuba esifanelekileyo phakathi kwezityalo ezimbini ngokuxhomekeka kwinjongo yazo: ucingo oluphilayo (1m), ukukhuselwa komhlaba (2m), ukuthintela umoya (3m), umthunzi (5m); Grumba imingxuma enzulu kwaye ebanzi ngokwaneleyo ukuze iingcambu zesityalo zibe nendawo eyaneleyo, zingaxinwanga, zinganyuswanga okanye zingaveli phezu komhlaba.

UKUNAKEKELA IZITYALO

Siyanivuyela! Nityale amakhulu emithi nezihlahla zemveli kuluntu lwenu! Sithembele ekubeni zonke ziya kuphila kwaye zisebenze ngendlela ebesiyicwangcisile. Ukunakekelwa okuyimfuneko kunyaka wokuqala kuya kunceda izityalo zibe nenkululeko yokuzimela. Ngexesha lonyaka wokuqala, ngakumbi ngehlobo (ukususela ngoDisemba 2024 ukuya kuAprili 2025), imithi iya kufuna ingqwalasela enkulu. Sicebisa ukuba izityalo zinkcenkeshelwe kanye ngeveki, ngelixa kukwaqwalaselwa nophuhliso lwazo lwempilo.

A. Ukuncenkeshela

Nkcnkeshela isityalo ude umsele osijikelezileyo ugcwale ngokupheleleyo. Oku kubonisa ukuba umhlaba ojikelezileyo unamanzi aneleyo ukufikelela kwimpande. Ukuba umsele awukho, zama ukuwudala ngokuhambisa umhlaba ojikeleze isiqu sesityalo ukwenza isangqa esiphakamileyo kancinci esiza kubamba amanzi.

Xa unkcenkeshela, hlola umhlaba. Ukuba uqhekekile okanye unzima kakhulu, oko kuthetha ukuba womile kakhulu kwaye ufuna amanzi ongezelelweyo. Ukuba umhlaba umtyibilizi kwaye unevumba, oko kuthetha ukuba manzi kakhulu, kufuneka uvunyelwe ukuba wome kancinci. Lungisa ubungakanani bamanzi ngokwemeko yomhlaba. Emva kokuncenkeshela, wugalela umhlaba ngomaleko wezinto ezomileyo ukunciphisa ukuphela kwamanzi nokuthintela ukhukuliseko lomhlaba.

B. Iimpande

Hlola ukuba iimpande zesityalo zimile ngokuqinileyo kwaye zifihlakele phantsi komhlaba. Ukuba kukho iimpande ezivele ngaphandle okanye ezihanjiswe yimpembelelo, yongeza umhlaba uze uwucinezele ngobunono usebenzisa izandla okanye izithende. Qinisekisa ukuba akukho magqabi okanye amasebe atshoniswe ngaphakathi komhlaba, kuba oko kungachaphazela impilo yesityalo.

Ukuba isityalo sisincinci kwaye sisondele emhlabeni, qinisekisa ukuba isangqa esingqongile isityalo sicoceke, singabi neengca nezinye izityalo ezincinci ezikhula ecaleni kwaso. Oku kuya kusinceda sifumane ukukhanya okwaneleyo, amanzi, kunye nezondlo zomhlaba ngaphandle kokhuphiswano. Ukuba isityalo sidlula kwinqanaba lengalo okanye sesingaphaya komphakama wamadolo, oku akusayi kuba yingxaki.

C. Isiqu Namagqabi

Ukuba isityalo silahle uninzi lwamagqabi kwaye kwasala isiqu sodwa, oku kunokuthetha ukuba sizikhusele kwiimeko ezinzima. Musa ukucinga ukuba sifile. Hlola isiqu ukuze ubone ukuba sisasetyenziswa kwaye siluhlaza. Ukuba isiqu asiqhekeki xa usigoba, zama ukukrwela ulusu lwaso ngobunono usebenzisa uziphoo; ukuba isaluhlaza ngaphakathi, oko kuthetha ukuba isityalo sisaphila kwaye sinokuphinda sihlume amagqabi xa iimeko ziba ngcono. Qhubeka usikhathalela njengesityalo esiphilayo.

Jonga isiqu namagqabi ukuze ubone naziphi na iimpawu zomonakalo. Ukuba ezi nxalenye zomile zaza zaqhekeka, isityalo singadinga amanzi amaninzi okanye umthunzi. Ukuba ezi nxalenye zinamabala anemibala eyahlukileyo, zinokuchaphazeleka sisifo sempande okanye amagqabi. Ukuba zinamachokoza, zinokuba zityiwa zizinambuzane. Bhalela phantsi ezi mpawu uze wazise iFarmer Forum.

Lungisa indlela yokuncenkeshela ukuba iimpande, isiqu, okanye amagqabi atyhafile. Tsala uphose amagqabi anemibala engafaniyo okanye awonakeleyo ukuphepha ukusasazeka kwesifo okanye ukwanda kwezimbuzane. Hlola isityalo ukuze ubone ukuba azikho okanye awekho amaqonya, iintethe, fungus, njl., kwaye uzisuse ngesandla.

D. Izinyathelo Zokuncedisa okanye ukungenelela

Ukuba izityalo zihlala zibonakalisa iimpawu zempilo embi (ukuyekelela, amabala, umonakalo) kangangeveki ezintathu zilandelelana, zinokufuna uncedo olongezelelekileyo. Ukuba izityalo ziyayekelela ngenxa yokufumana ilanga elingakumbi okanye umoya onamandla, kunokuba luncedo ukubeka inetha lomthunzi ujikeleze zona. Ukuba izityalo zinesifo okanye zinogcino lwezimbuzane, zinokufuna ukufakelwa kwenye indawo ngexesha lasekwindla. Ukuba iimpawu zesifo zisasazeka kwezinye izityalo kule veiki, izityalo ezosulelekileyo kufuneka zisuswe kwindawo yokutyala ngokukhawuleza.

Kwimeko yezimo zezulu ezingaqhelekanga ezifana nobushushu obuphezulu kakhulu okanye imvula enkulu, hlola izityalo kwakamsinya nje ukuba iimeko ziqheleke kwakhona. Sebenzisa amanyathelo angentla ukuqinisekisa ukuba izityalo zikwimeko entle.

Amanyathelo Alandelayo ka-2025

Iqela leprojekthi liza kubuya ngoFebruwari 2025 ukuze lilandelele izityalo kwaye lixoxe noluntu malunga nezinto esizifundayo. Siza kwenza le misebenzi ilandelayo kunye:

1. Ukubala izityalo nokujonga impilo yazo

Xa sasityala ngoNovemba 2024, sabala inani lezityalo ezazibekwe kwiindawo ezahlukeneyo. Ukuze siqonde ukuba senza ukhetho olufanelekileyo lwezityalo, siza kubala ukuba zingaphi izityalo ezisindileyo, zingaphi ezingasindanga, kwaye sijonge imeko yezempilo yesityalo ngasinye. Siza kuphawula ukuba ngaba kukho izityalo ezihlaselwe zizifo okanye izinambuzane njengoko kuchaziwe ngasentla.

2. Ukulinganisa impilo kunye nobubanzi besiqu sezityalo eziphawuliweyo ukuze zilandelelwe ixesha elide

NgoNovemba 2024, siphawule ezinye izityalo ngetheyiphu etyheli kwaye salinganisa ukuphakama kwazo kunye nobubanzi besiqu emazantsi. Siza kuphinda sithathe olu linganiso kwezi zityalo zinye ngoFebruwari 2025. Oku kuza kusinceda siqonde isantya sokukhula kwezityalo, ukuze siqikelele ixesha apho ziya kuvuthwa kwaye ziqale ukuvelisa iziqhamo.

3. Ukuxoxa ngezinto esizifundileyo kunye nezicwangciso

Siza kuxoxa kunye ngezinto esizibonileyo malunga nemozulu kunye neemeko zezityalo kwezi nyanga zintathu. Siza kugqiba indlela yokoyisa nayiphi na imiceli mngeni esinokuhlangabezana nayo, kunye nokucwangcisa indlela esiza kuzinakekela ngayo izityalo. Siza kubhala phantsi zonke izinto esizifundileyo kunye nezicwangciso zethu.

UKUJONGA IXESHA ELIDE

Sityale izityalo ezingama-2747 kwiindawo ezingama-22 ngoNovemba 2024 (Jonga Itheyibhile 1). Kungangcono ukuba silandelele inani lezityalo ezisindayo okanye eziphilayo, kunye nendlela ezikhula ngayo rhoqo ngexesha lonyaka. Iqela leprojekthi liza kutyelela ngoFebruwari nangoMeyi 2025 ukuze lilandelele ezi zityalo kwaye libonise uluntu indlela abanokulandelela ngayo ukukhula kwezityalo kwixesha elizayo.

Iqela leprojekthi liphawule izityalo ezingama-124 kwiindawo ezisibhozo ukuze zijongwe ixesha elide. Ezi zityalo zine-theyiphu etyheli ebophelezwe kuzo, enamagama ezityalo ezibhalwe kuyo ngokwesayensi. Ezi zityalo sele zilinganisiwe kwaye ziya kuqhubeka zilinganiswa ngokwe-root collar diameter (rcd) kunye nobude bazo bubonke. Olu lungelelwaniso lunika ulwazi olubalulekileyo malunga nokukhula kunye nempilo yezityalo eziselula. Injongo ephambili kolu vavanyo kukumisela isantya sokukhula kwezi ntlobo zezityalo, nto leyo eya kusinika umkhomba wokuba ezi ntlobo zisempilweni, kwaye oko kuya kuvumela ukuthelekisa nesantya sokukhula kwezityalo ezihlumayo kwezinye iindawo.

Itheyibhile 1: Uluhlu lweendawo kunye nenani lezityalo ezityalwe kule projekthi kwiindawo ezintandathu zoluntu lwase-Amadiba.

Indawo	Ityalwe (n)	Izityalo Zokujonga (n)	Ubukhulu (ha)	Uluntu	Itotali Yezityalo Zasekuhlaleni (n)
Mdatya School	102	20 (Approx)	2.3	Mdatya	346
Sijadu School	155	20 (Approx)	7.9		
Mdatya Erosion	89	0	0.6		
Bhekela School	371	0	0.9	Bhekela	371
Mtolani Community Garden	75	16	0.2	Mtolani	361
Mtolani Nursery	41	4	0.02		
Mnyameni Homestay	49	3	0.4		
Dukisa Homestead	34	0	0.1		
Komkhulu Community Centre	162	0	na		
Kwanyana Lodge	121	0	1.0	Mphindweni	443
Kwanyana Community Garden and Nursery	104	0	1.3		
Mthwa Homestead	40	0	0.2		
Xolobeni School	50	16	3.2		
Trayi Homestead	128	0	0.06		
Sikhombe Dunes	283	0	2.5	Nyavini	680
Dumasi Hall	183	0	0.3		
Dumasi Creche	112	18	0.08		
Six Community Gardens	102	0	0.03		
Masizame Creche	84	0	0.3	Gobodweni	546
Baleni School	166	27	3.7		
Amadiba Community Network Centre	229	0	0.3		
Mzwandile Nursery	67	0	0.1		
Total	2747	124 (Approx)	25.5		2747

Ukulinganisa izityalo ezincinci kulula, kusetyenziswa intambo yokulinganisa. I-root collar yinxalenye yesiqu sesityalo ephuma emhlabeni. Eli candelo libhijelwe ngetheyiphu kwaye lilinganiswa umjikelo walo. I-root collar diameter (rcd) ibalwa ngokwahlula umjikelo ngo-3.14. Ubude besityalo buqala ukusuka kwi-root collar ukuya kwindawo ephakamileyo kwisityalo. Kwiimeko apho isityalo sineziqu ezininzi, isiqu esibanzi kakhulu siya kulinganiswa nge-rcd, kwaye owona msonto uphakamileyo weso sityalo uya kulinganiswa ubude. Itheyibhile A ekupheleni kwale ncwadana ibonisa amaxabiso obukhulu bezityalo ezityalwe kule projekthi.

Ukuba isityalo sikhule sadlula iimitha ezimbini, sinokulinganiswa ngendlela elula kusetyenziswa irula, intambo yokulinganisa, kunye nabantu ababini. Kuqinisekiswa ukuba umphantsi apho ume khona awukho kwithambeka, ukuze ungabi phezulu kakhulu okanye phantsi kakhulu xa uthlekisa nesisityalo. Phakamisa irula ngesandla, ime nkqo emhlabeni. Yolula ingalo phambili, ingqamane nomhlaba. Hamba kancinci usuka esityalweni ide irula nesityalo zibonakale zilingana ngobude. Phawula indawo omi kuyo emhlabeni. Sebenzisa intambo yokulinganisa ukuhlola umgama ukusuka kwindawo omi kuyo ukuya kwi-root collar yesityalo. Lo mgama uphantse walingana nobude besityalo.

Iqela leprojekthi lizakuzama ukuzisa i-clinometer ukuze kuhlolwe ubude bezityalo ngendlela echanileyo, baze bafundise uluntu indlela yokuyisebenzisa xa belinganisa izityalo ezinde. Xa sele sinezilinganiso ezintathu (ngoJuni 2025), siya kuqala ukubala izinga lokukhula kweentlobo zezityalo ezahlukeneyo. Oku kuyakusivumela ukuba siqikelele ukuba kungathatha iminyaka emingaphi ukuba isityalo sibe nesivuno okanye sifikelele kwinqanaba lokuvuthwa. Umzekelo:

- Siyazi ukuba *Harpephyllum caffrum* (umgwenye) ufikelela ekukhuleni okupheleleyo xa sele unobude obuziimitha ezisixhenxe (7m).
- Xa besityala, sasine-37cm. NgoFebruwari 2025, sakhula saya kwi-81cm. NgoMeyi 2025, sakhula saya kwi-123cm.
- Ke ngoko, isityalo sikhule i-44cm ehlotyeni, i-42cm ekwindla, ngomlinganiselo we-43cm kwikota.
- Oku kuthetha ukuba isityalo sikhula i-14.3cm ngenyanga, kwaye malunga ne-171.6cm ngonyaka.
- Ngokukhula ngolu hlobo, isityalo siza kufikelela kubude be-7m, kwaye ngaloo ndlela sifikelele ekuvuthweni, kwiminyaka emine ezayo.

UKUSETYENZISWA OKUZINZILEYO

Xa isityalo sele sikhule ngokupheleleyo, siya kuqala ukuvelisa iziqhamo ngamaxesha athile onyaka. Isantya saso sokukhula, esitshintshe kakhulu ebusheni baso, siya kuthoba. Isityalo sinokwanda ngobubanzi, ngesiqu esimbaxa kunye neengcambu neengalo ezisasazeka kakhulu, kunokuba zikhule phezulu. Izityalo ezikhule ngokupheleleyo zininzi iindawo ezininzi eziluncedo, ezifana: Iziqhamo, Iintyatyambo, Amagqabi, Imbewu, Umthi kunye neengcambu. Indlela yokukhetha nokuqokelela iinxalenye zesityalo kunye namaxesha afanelekileyo okuvuna ziya kufumaneka kwincwadi yeentlobo zezityalo eziza kuziswa liqela leprojekthi ngoFebruwari 2025.

Imigaqo esisiseko xa kuvunwa izityalo:

1. Musa ukwenzakalisa iingcambu okanye intonga yesityalo, kuba ezi nxalenye zibalulekile ekuphuhliseni nasekusindiseni isityalo. Xa uthatha umthi, khetha iindibano ezincinci ezikude nomqolo, endaweni yokusika amasebe amakhulu asondele emqolweni wesityalo. Xa uthatha umqolo wesiqu okanye iingcambu, qaphela kwaye uthabathe inxenyane encinci kuphela. Sukukhupha ngaphezulu kwesinye kwisine (1/4) somjikelo wesebe, isiqu, okanye ingcambu, ukuze isityalo sikwazi ukuzihlaziya.
2. Thabatha kuphela into oyidingayo, okanye ubuncinci isiqingatha zesityalo ezinje ngeziqhamo, iintyatyambo, namagqabi. Khumbula ukuba isityalo sisebenzisa ezi nxalenye ukwenza ukutya kwaso, kwaye sidinga imbewu yaso ukuze sande. Ezinye izilwanyana, iintaka, kunye nezinambuzane zithembe kwezi zityalo zokutya kwazo – ke ngoko, vuna ngobuchule ukuze kungabikho monakalo kwindalo esingqongileyo.
3. Sebenzisa izandla zakho xa unokuqokelela amagqabi athambileyo, iziqhamo, okanye ezinye iinxalenye ezifunekayo. Xa usebenzisa imela okanye isarha ukusika umthi okanye umqolo, yenza ukusika okucocekileyo kwaye ngokukhawuleza ukuze unciphise ukwenzakala kwesityalo. Xa iziqhamo okanye amagqabi engekho kufikeleleka, sebenzisa ileli okanye isixhobo sokukhupha iziqhamo. Ezinye izityalo ziwisa iziqhamo ezivuthiweyo ngokwazo – zama ukuzibamba ngengubo okanye inetha ephakanyisiweyo, ukuze unciphise ukwenzakala kweziqhamo ngenxa yokuwela emhlabeni okanye ukuhlaselwa zizilwanyana kunye nezinambuzane.

UKUZALANA KWEZITYALO

Uninzi lwezityalo esizaziyo zizivelisela zona ngokuzala imbewu. Le mbewu ihlala ikhula ngaphakathi kwesityalo. Isityalo kufuneka sivelise iintyatyambo, ezitshintshela uthuli lweentyatyambo phakathi kwecandelo lesidoda nelamaqanda okanye isinina, ze emva koko zivelise isiqhamo. Uninzi lweentyatyambo zezityalo lunezinto zesidoda nezamanqanda, nto leyo ethetha ukuba isityalo sinokuzivelisela iintyatyambo, iziqhamo, nembewu sodwa. Iinyosi, izinambuzane, kunye neentaka ezisela iintyatyambo ezifana neengcungcu zinceda ekushintshiseni uthuli lweentyatyambo ukusuka kwicandelo lesidoda ukuya kwicandelo lamanqanda leentyatyambo.

Nangona kunjalo, ezinye izityalo zinemithi yamadoda neyabasetyhini eyahlukileyo, kwaye ngamanye amaxesha, uhlobo olunye lweentyatyambo lukhula kwesityalo esinye. Kwesi simo, isityalo esinesidoda sidinga iinyosi, izinambuzane, okanye iintaka ukuze zithuthe uthuli lweentyatyambo ukuya kwesityalo esinamanqanda esiqhakazileyo, nangokunjalo. Kuphela xa isityalo somfazi sithe sakhwelwa luthuli lweentyatyambo apho sinokukwazi ukuvelisa iziqhamo nembewu.

Kukho olunye uhlobo lwezityalo apho ukuqhama, ukuvelisa iziqhamo, kunye nokuzala imbewu kwenzeka kabuhlungu, kwaye ezi zityalo zihlala ziziphindaphinda ngokukhupha izithole. Izithole zingcambu ezincinci ezikwaziyo ukukhula ngokukhawuleza, zize zohlukane nesityalo somzali, size kwenzeka isityalo esitsha esifana nesityalo somzali.

Masikhangele kwiindlela ezahlukeneyo esinokuthi sizisebenzise ukuvumela izityalo zethu ukuba zizalane.

Sithe satyala iintlobo zezityalo ezingama-32 kummandla wase-Amadiba (Jonga Itheyibhile 2). Kwezi, iintlobo ezingama-20 zingakhula lula kwimbewu. Iintlobo ezisibhozo (8) kwezingama-32 zizi-dioecious, okuthetha ukuba zonke iintyatyambo kwesityalo esinye zizezesidoda okanye zamaqanda kuphela. Ngoko ke, ezi zityalo zifuna ubuncinane izityalo ezimbini ezikufutshane ukuze zikwazi ukuvelisa iziqhamo. Sithembe ukuba ubuncinane esinye kwezi zityalo siyahluka kwezinye. Ukuba iziqhamo azivelisi kwisizini ethile, kufuneka kutyalwe esinye isityalo esitsha esingahambelani nezityalo ezingavelisanga iziqhamo (oko kukuthi, esityalwe kwimbewu).

Ezine (4) kwezi zityalo zingama-32 kulula ukuziphindaphinda ngamasebe kunokuzityala kwimbewu. Izityalo ezityalwe ngamasebe zidla ngokufana ngokupheleleyo nezityalo zazo zomzali, ngoko kufuneka kusikwe kuphela kwiintyatyalo ezisempilweni, ezinamandla, nezikwaziyo ukumelana nemeko ezinzima.

1. Ukuzalana ngembewu

1.1. Imbewu entsha

Eyona ndlela yokutyalwa isityalo kwimbewu yaso kukusebenzisa isiqhamo esivuthiweyo. Coca inyama yesiqhamo esivuthiweyo, uze utyale imbewu kwi-1 ukuya kwi-2 intshi yomhlaba. Beka imbewu ngendlela eya kufumana ukukhanya kwelanga kodwa ikhuseleke kwimvula enamandla okanye umoya onamandla. Iimbewu ze-ilala kunye ne-umphafa (*Hyphaene coriacea* kunye *Ziziphus mucronata*) kufuneka zivulwe kwi-nut yazo. Iimbewu ze-umthongwane, injomi, umkuhlu, kunye ne-umphafa (*Englerophytum natalense*, *Syzygium cordatum*, *Trichilia emetica*, *Ziziphus mucronata*) kufuneka zibe zintsha xa zityalwa, oko kukuthi, azinakuginwa kwisizini edlulileyo.

Cinga ngendawo yesiqhelo yesityalo kunye nemozulu yangoku xa ugqiba ukuba ungayiniselela okanye nkcenkceshela kangakanani imbewu emva kokuyityala. Izityalo ezifuna ukufuma okanye umfumo okuphakathi zingafumanzwa kube kanye ngeveki, ngelixa ezo zidinga umhlaba ongalulanga kakhulu zihlala zijongwa kwaye zilungiswa ukufuma kwazo imihla ngemihla. Itheyibhile 2 inikezela ngemiyalelo malunga nobungakanani bokuncenkceshela kunye nexesha lokuhluma kwezinye izityalo. Emva kokuba imbewu ihlumile, izithole kufuneka zikhuselwe kwimozulu embi de zifikelele kubude obuyi-50cm. Emva kweli nqanaba, zingatyalwa kwiindawo ezivulekileyo njengoko kufanelekile.

1.2. Imbewu ephathwe ngeendlela ezithile

Ezinye iimbewu ezintsha (*Diospyros whyteana*, *Mimusops zeyheri*) zifuna ukusikwa kancinane okanye ukukhuhlwa ukuze ziqale ukuvuthwa. Khuhla ulwelwe lwembewu kancinci ngelitye, ifayile yenzipho, okanye incam yebhleyidi ukuze ululazise. Qinisekisa ukuba ukukhuhla kwenziwa ngobunono ngadluli elulweleni lwembewu. Emva koko, yityale njengesiqhelo. Ezinye iimbewu ezintsha ezifana nezozizimisi-umqokolo, umpayi, kunye ne-umthumbu (*Dovyalis caffra*, *Ficus natalensis*, *Ficus sur*) kufuneka zomise emthunzini kangangeeyure ezingama-24 ngaphambi kokutyalwa emhlabeni.

Ezinye iimbewu ezintsha ezinolwelwe oluqinileyo kufuneka zifakwe emanzini ubusuku bonke ukuze ziqale ukuvuthwa. Iimbewu ze-umdubu, umgwenya, umsimbithi, kunye ne-umkuhlu (*Combretum erythrophyllum*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Milletia grandis*, *Trichilia emetica*) kufuneka zifakwe emanzini aqhelekileyo ubusuku bonke.

Iimbewu ze-umgadankawu, Amathungula, umbhongisa, kunye ne-umphafa (*Albizia adianthifolia*, *Carissa spp*, *Diospyros lycoides*, *Ziziphus mucronata*) kufuneka zifakwe emanzini afudumeleyo ubusuku bonke. Qinisekisa ukuba amanzi ashushu kodwa engatshisi kakhulu. Iimbewu ezifakwe emanzini zide zibe buthathaka kwaye zande zikulungele ukutyalwa emhlabeni.

Itheyibhile 2: Iindlela Zokuvelisa Izityalo Kwiintlobo Ezityalwe Kuluntu Lwe-Amadiba Oluthandathu (6)

Igama Lezityalo	Igama LesiXhosa	Eyona Ndlela Ingcono Yokuvelisa	Indlela Yesibini	Indlela Yesithathu	Ixesha Lokuntshula	Ubungakanani Bamanzi
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu, umhlandlothi	imbewu entsha efakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke	imbewu egciniweyo ukuya kuthi ga kwiinyanga ezi-3 ifakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke			ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umNini	imbewu entsha			5-9 iintsuku	ukukhanya
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini	imbewu entsha			iinyanga ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-3	ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	imbewu entsha okanye egciniweyo (ukuya kuthi ga kunyaka o-1) ifakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke	izithole (cuttings)	ukuqinisa umqolo emoyeni	iinyanga ezi-2	ukukhanya; ukumelana nembalela
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	imbewu entsha okanye egciniweyo (ukuya kuthi ga kunyaka o-1) ifakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke	izithole (cuttings)	ukuqinisa umqolo emoyeni	7-14 iintsuku	
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	imbewu entsha okanye egciniweyo (ukuya kuthi ga kunyaka o-1) ifakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke	izithole (cuttings)	ukuqinisa umqolo emoyeni		ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	imbewu entsha efakwe emanzini ubusuku bonke			7-14 iintsuku	
<i>Cordia caffra</i>		imbewu			14 iintsuku	ukukhanya
<i>Diospyros lycioides</i>	umbhongisa	imbewu efakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke				
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	imbewu ekufuneka ikrwitshwe/sacrificed ngaphambi kokutyala			iiveki ezi-4 ukuya kwezi-8	ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	umqokolo	imbewu ecocekileyo neyomileyo ethunzi	izithole (cuttings)		iintsuku ezi-18 ukuya kwezi-20	
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umThongwane	imbewu entsha			iiveki ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-3	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	amahlahla (truncheons)	izithole (cuttings)	imbewu		ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umpayi, amakhiwane	izithole (cuttings)	imbewu			ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Ficus sur</i>	umthumbu, amakhiwane	ukuqinisa umqolo emoyeni (air layering)	izithole (cuttings)	imbewu	iintsuku ezi-15 ukuya kwezi-20	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	imbewu	ukutyala izityalo ezihlanganisiweyo		iinyanga ezi-6	
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	imbewu				ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	imbewu	izithole (cuttings)	amahlahla (truncheons)	iiveki ezi-6	ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenya	imbewu efakwe emanzini ubusuku bonke	izithole (cuttings)	amahlahla (truncheons)	iintsuku ezi-7 ukuya kwezi-11	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Hoslundia opposita</i>		imbewu	izithole (cuttings)			ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	izithole (cuttings)	imbewu (cuttings)		iiveki ezi-8	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Hyphaene coriacea</i>	ilala	izithole (suckers)	imbewu eqhekekileyo		iintsuku ezi-14 ukuya kwiintsuku ezi-180	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Milletia grandis</i>	umsimbeeti	imbewu entsha efakwe emanzini ubusuku bonke				ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>		imbewu entsha	imbewu egciniweyo ekrwitshiweyo ngaphambi kokutyala		iiveki ezi-2	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	izithole (suckers)	imbewu		iinyanga ezi-2 ukuya kwezi-3	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Portulacaria afro</i>	igqwanitsha	izithole (cuttings)			iiveki ezi-4 ukuya kwezi-6	ukukhanya
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga, ikhamanga	izithole (suckers)	imbewu			ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Syzigium cordatum</i>	injomi, umdoni	imbewu entsha			iintsuku ezi-25	ifuna amanzi amaninzi
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	izithole (cuttings)	imbewu entsha			ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkuhlu	imbewu entsha efakwe emanzini ubusuku bonke	izithole (suckers)	ukuqinisa umqolo emoyeni	iintsuku ezi-10 ukuya kwezi-20	ubungakanani obuphakathi
<i>Vangueria infausta</i>	amavilo	izithole (suckers)	imbewu	izithole		
<i>Ziziphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	imbewu entsha efakwe emanzini ashushu ubusuku bonke			iintsuku ezi-7 ukuya kwezi-14	ubungakanani obuphakathi

1.3. Imbewu egciniweyo

limbewu zezityalo ezithile zinokugcinwa kwisizini enye, okanye de kube kunyaka omnye. Iimbewu ze-umgandankawu, amathungula, umbinza, umgwenya, ilala, mavilo, kunye ne-red milkwood (*Albizia adianthifolia*, *Carissa spp.*, *Halleria lucida*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Hyphaene coriacea*, *Vangueria infausta*, *Mimusops zeyheri*) zingagcinwa ixesha elide. Xa ugcina imbewu, qinisekisa ukuba isuswe yonke into engaphezulu or okanye isivalo kwayo/sayo, yomiswe emthunzini kangangeeyure ezingama-24 okanye ngaphezulu, yaye igcinwe kwindawo epholileyo, eyomileyo, nevulekileyo kodwa engafumani ilanga elithe ngqo. Ukufakwa kwelanga, ukufuma, okanye izinambuzane kungonakalisa imbewu egciniweyo, ngoko kufuneka ugcine imbewu kwindawo ecocekileyo, eyomileyo, nesemthunzini. Xa usebenzisa imbewu egciniweyo ukuze utyale, qinisekisa ukuba ayingenwanga zizinambuzane. Imbewu egciniweyo ye-red milkwood (*Mimusops zeyheri*) kufuneka ikrwitshiswe okanye ikhuhlwe kancinane ngaphambi kokutyala. Yonke imbewu egciniweyo kufuneka ifakwe emanzini afudumele ubusuku bonke ukuze iqale ukuvuthwa. Qinisekisa ukuba amanzi afudumele kodwa engatshisi kakhulu. Emva koko, yityale njengesiqhelo.

2. Ukuvelisa Izityalo Ngokusikwa

2.1. Izithole

Ezinye izityalo zivelisa izithole ngokwendalo, ezizezona ziqukatho zesityalo ezivelayo phantsi komhlaba. Iingcambu zesityalo zithumela intshulube entsha ejongeka kwaye iziphatha njengesityalo esitsha ecaleni kwesityalo esikhulileyo. Esi sithole sinokukhutshwa ngobunono kwisityalo esidala kwaye sityalwe kwindawo oyinqwenelayo. Ukusika isithole kwisityalo esikhulileyo, thambisa umhlaba ojikeleze iingcambu zesithole uze usenze ukusikwa okucocekileyo ukuze uhlukanise isithole kwisityalo somzali. Zama ukungaphazami isityalo somzali kangangoko kunokwenzeka. Xa ufaka isithole kwindawo entsha, qinisekisa ukuba zonke iingcambu zaso zigcinwe zilungelelaniswe njengoko kuchaziwe kumgaqo-nkqubo wokutyala. Izityalo ezifana ne-ilala, isundu, skamanga, umkuhlu, kunye namavilo (*Hyphaene coriacea*, *Phoenix reclinata*, *Strelitzia nicolai*, *Trichillia emetica*, *Vangueria infausta*) zivelisa izithole. Izithole zivelisa izityalo ezifanayo nesityalo somzali, kwaye ilala kunye nesundu zii-dioecious. Oko kuthetha ukuba isundu esiyinkunzi siya kuvelisa isithole esiyinkunzi, ngoko ke ukuze siphehle iziqhamo, kuya kufuneka kube khona isundu esingumfazi kufutshane. Kucetyiswa ukuba oku kuthathelwe ingqalelo xa kutyalwa imithi yesundu ukuze ibe neziqhamo.

2.2. Ukusika

Ukusika ziindawo zomqolo wesityalo ezithathwa kwisityalo esikhulileyo kwaye zikhuthazwa ukuba zivelise iingcambu ukuze zibe zizityalo ezizimeleyo. Ukusikwa kuthathwa kumqolo osele uzinzile, ngokuhlelekileyo ngokususa ingalo eguqukayo esuka ezantsi kwesiqu esiphambili. Le ngalo ingaba nobude obuphakathi kwe-5 ukuya kwi-15cm kwaye kufuneka iqulathe inxalenye yesiqu esikhulu (ebizwa ngokuba yi-heel) kunye nebud elinye, ngcono ukuba libekwe phezulu. Le ngalo kufuneka isikwe ngentsimbi ebukhali okanye imela ebukhali ngokusika kanye kwii-45 degrees ukusuka kwisiqu esikhulu, ngenjongo yokunciphisa umonakalo. Amagqabi nawuphi na omnye umphunga okufutshane ne-heel kufuneka asuswe, kwaye i-heel ifakwe kwikhompawundi ekhuthaza iingcambu ukuba ikhona. Beka ukusikwa emthunzini ophakathi, ungakutyali phantsi kwelanga elithe ngqo. Londoloza imbewu efanelekileyo yokukhula njengoko kuchaziwe kumgaqo-nkqubo wokuvelisa izityalo ngembewu. Ukukhula kweengcambu kuthatha inyanga enye, emva koko ukusikwa kuba sisityalo ezizimeleyo esinokuthi sihlale siphila kwiimeko zangaphandle.

Izityalo ezifana namathungula, umqokolo, umsinsi, umpayi (okanye amakhiwane), umthumbu, amabimbi, umbinza, umgwenya, orange bird-berry, uthongothi, spekboom (iqgwantsha), iboza, kunye namavilo (*Carissa spp.*, *Dovyalis caffra*, *Erythrina lysistemon*, *Ficus natalensis*, *Ficus sur*, *Garcinia livingstonei*, *Halleria lucida*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Hoslundia opposita*, *Hyperacanthus amoenus*,

Portulacaria afra, *Tetradenia riparia*, *Vangueria infausta*) zingaveliswa ngokusika. Qaphela: Amathungula, umqokolo, amabimbi, kunye nomgwenya zi-dioecious, oko kuthetha ukuba ukusikwa kwazo kuya kuvelisa isityalo esinekhono elifanayo (umqokolo oyinkunzi uya kuvelisa umqokolo oyinkunzi). Kuthathelwe ingqalelo oku xa ufuna iziqhamo.

2.3. Amasebe Apeheleleyo

Amasebe apeheleleyo yimiqolo epeheleleyo yesityalo ethathwa kwisityalo esivuthiweyo kwaye ikhuthazwa ukuba ivelise izityalo ezizimeleyo ezifanayo nomzali. La masebe ahluka kancinane kwizinto ezisikiweyo (cuttings) kuba ende (iimitha ezi-1 ukuya kwezi-2 ubude) kwaye inombindi oqinileyo. Inkqubo yokuthatha i-truncheon: Sika isebe kwisiqu esikhulu nge45-degree cut ezicace gca. Bekela bucala amasebe emthunzini iyure ezingama-24 ukuze uphume umoya, kodwa ungawushihi ixesha elide kakhulu. Susa amagqabi nawuphi na omnye umphunga kwi-50cm yokuqala yamasebe. Faka isebe (heel) emhlabeni ngokusifaka nzulu, uqinisekise ukuba simile nkqo kwaye sikhuselwe xa kuyimfuneko. Londoloza isebe njengoko kuchaziwe kwicandelo lokukhathalela izityalo. Ixesha elifanelekileyo lokuthatha i-truncheon: Entwasahlobo okanye ekuweni. Izityalo ezifana nomsinsi, umbinza, umgwenya, kunye nomkuhlu (*Erythrina lysistemon*, *Halleria lucida*, *Harpephyllum caffrum*, *Trichillia emetica*) zingaveliswa nge-truncheons. Qaphela: I-truncheons zivelisa izityalo ezifanayo nomzali. Umgwenya yi-dioecious, ngoko ke i-truncheon ethathwe kwisityalo esiyinkunzi iya kuba yinkunzi, kwaye esivela kwisityalo esingumfazi siya kuba ngumfazi. Kuthathelwe ingqalelo oku xa ufuna iziqhamo.

2.4. Ukuvelisa Izityalo Ngokuqinisa Umqolo Emoyeni (air layering)

Ukuvelisa izityalo ngokuqinisa umqolo emoyeni yinkqubo ekhuthaza ingalo yesityalo ukuba ikhulise iingcambu kwaye iphuhlise isityalo ezizimeleyo, ngelixa isanamathele kwisityalo somzali. Indlela yokwenza i-air layering: Khetha umqolo othe tyaba, oqinileyo, nosele uzinzile, onokuthi wahlukane kamva ngaphandle kokulimaza isityalo. Khetha indawo emalunga ne-50cm kude nesiphelo salo mqolo, apho iingcambu ziya kuveliswa khona. Susa amagqabi kulo mmandla kwaye ususe ixolo lwesiqithi usebenzisa imela ebukhali. Ixolo kufuneka lususe jikelele kwisiqu kwaye kubude obumalunga ne-5cm, ukuze umphakathi otyheli-luhlaza (cambium layer) ubonakale. Faka iziyobisi zokukhuthaza iingcambu kule ndawo ukuba zikhona. Songa ibhegi yeplastiki ecaleni kwale ndawo, usebenzisa irabha, intambo okanye i-cable tie. Gcwalisa ibhegi yeplastiki ngesikhuseleli sengcambu esimanzi, esinokubakho njenge-sphagnum moss, okanye umxube kunye nomhlaba wokutyala izityalo. Qinisekisa ukuba ibhegi igubungela ngokupheleleyo indawo eveziweyo, kwaye uvale ibhegi kakuhle ngaphezulu.

Lo mqolo unokuthatha inyanga enye ukuya kunyaka omnye ukuba ukhule iingcambu ngaphakathi kwebhegi. Gcina indawo imanzi kwaye ujonge rhoqo ngeveki ukukhula kweengcambu. Qaphela iimpawu zesifo njengoko kuchazwe kwicandelo lokunyamekela izityalo. Xa iingcambu zifika kwi-5cm ubude, isityalo sikulungele ukwahlulwa kwisityalo somzali kwaye sityalwe emhlabeni. Ixesha elifanelekileyo lokwenza i-air layering yintwasahlobo okanye ukuwa. Amathungula, umthumbu okanye amakhiwane, kunye nomkuhlu (*Carissa spp.*, *Ficus sur*, *Trichillia emetica*). Izityalo eziveliswe ngale ndlela ziyafanayo nezityalo zomzali. Qaphela: Amathungula sisityalo esiyi-dioecious, oko kuthetha ukuba isityalo esitsha esivelisweyo siza kuba sisini esifanayo nesityalo somzali (ukuba ngumqokolo oyinkunzi okanye oyinkazana).

3. Iimbono Ngokubanzi

Sikhethe izityalo ezikhula ngokwendalo kwaye ezihambelana kakuhle nemeko yendalo yengingqi yaseAmadiba. Xa kutyalwa kwezinye iindawo, kuthathelwe ingqalelo. Ubushushu obufanelekileyo kunye nemvula isityalo esinokuthi siphile phantsi kwayo. Ubungakanani bokukhanya kunye nodidi lomhlaba isityalo esilithandayo. Ubude obukude nolwandle kunye neemeko zomoya ezinokuthi ziphazamise isityalo. Ulwazi oluninzi lufumaneka kwiThebhile 3 engezantsi.

Itheyibhile 3: Limeko zokukhula kwezityalo ezityalwe kwiindawo ezintandathu zaseAmadiba

Igama Lezityalo	Igama LesiXhosa	Ukwenzeka Kwengingqi	Ubushushu	Imvula	Ukukhanya	Umlaba	Uvakalelo	Izinga lokukhula
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu, umhlandlothi	Kumahlathi asezingqeni nasemazantsi, kwimida yamahlathi, kumahlathi avulekileyo nasezintlini (gorges) eziphakathi kwama-250m nama-450m	22 - 28°C (inyamezela i-15 - 34°C)	1,500 - 2,500mm (inyamezela i-900 - 4,000mm)	ilanga eligcweleyo	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 4 - 7	iqabaka	2m ngonyaka
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	Kwiindawo ezinehlathi, iBushveld, kwiindawo ezinamawa, nakwiingxangxasi zamanzi kunye nemilambo	12 - 36°C	0 - 35mm neveki	ilanga eligcweleyo	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 6.5	iqabaka	phakathi
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	umvutshwama, umyushulube, umvuthwamini	Kwiindidi ezahlukeneyo zeendawo eziphilayo, kuquka amahlathi aselunxwemeni nakwiinduli, amahlathi akumhlaba oneenduli, imida yamahlathi, i-bushveld kunye neengca ezinamawa, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,700m	imozulu epholileyo		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, udongwe, umhlaba othambileyo	ayinakukwazi ukusinda kwiimeko zembalela	ukukhula ngokukhawuleza emva kokuntshula
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	Iindawo ezinehlathi, emaphethelweni ehlati, nakwiinduli zolwandle, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,600m	i-tropical kunye ne-sub-tropical (25°C umndilili)		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 6.5	kancinane ukumelana neqabaka	300mm ngonyaka, ikhula kwi-2 - 3 iminyaka
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	Ifumaneka kwiindawo ezincinci nakwiithana ekufuphi nolwandle, ukuya kubude obungange-2,000m	19 - 30°C	1000 - 2,100mm	ilanga eligcweleyo	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle		1 - 2m ngonyaka, ikhula kwi-4 - 5 iminyaka
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	Amahlathi aselunxwemeni, nakwiindawo ezahlukeneyo zobude kunye nobubanzi	23 - 28°C (inyamezela i-10 - 34°C)	800 - 1,200mm (inyamezela i-600 - 1,800mm)	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo, pH 5 - 8	iqabaka	500 - 700mm ngonyaka, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-3
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	Kwiindawo ezinehlathi elomileyo okanye i-savanna, ngakumbi emilanjani, ukuya kuma-1,500m ngaphezu kolwandle	10 - 35°C		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo	ukumelana nembalela neqabaka	ikhula ngokukhawuleza, ikhula kwiminyaka emi-3
<i>Cordia caffra</i>		Iinduli ezinehlathi nakwiindawo zamahlathi aselunxwemeni. Uqheleke ngakumbi ngaphakathi ezweni, kwiindawo ezinehlathi elomileyo nakumda wamahlathi	10 - 35°C		umthunzi ukuya kwilanga elipheleleyo	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 4 - 7	kancinane imbalela ephakathi	500 - 750mm ngonyaka, ikhula kwi-5 - 7 iminyaka
<i>Diospyros lycioides</i>	umbhongisa	Ngasemilanjani, emilanjani, emahlathini, nakwi thickets ukuya ku 1,000m	10 - 35°C		ilanga eligcweleyo	umhlaba okhupha kakuhle amanzi		ikhula kancinci, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-4
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	Soloko uluhlaza, montane, kwihlathana ukuya ku 2,400m	10 - 35°C		ilanga, umthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle		ikhula kancinci
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	umqokolo	Kwiindawo ezomileyo, kwiindawo ezinengca enehlathi, nakwiimphetho zamahlathi, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,450m	10 - 35°C ipholile ukuya kwitropiki	700 - 1,300mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 5 - 7		600mm ngonyaka, ikhula kwi-4 - 5 iminyaka
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	Ihlathi lemvela, amahlathi asemilanjani, iintlambo ezinzulu kunye namahlathi aselunxwemeni, nakumahlathi, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,800m	imozulu epholileyo		umthunzi, umthunzi ophakathi	umhlaba okhupha kakuhle amanzi kwiindawo ezinamanzi amaninzi phantsi komhlaba	iqabaka	ikhula kancinci, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-6
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	Iindawo enengca enomthi; amahlathi aphulukana namagqabi ngamaxesha athile; amahlathi avulekileyo; iidune zesanti eziselunxwemeni; ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,950m ngaphezu kolwandle	10 - 35°C		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo	iqabaka	ikhula ngokukhawuleza
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umpayi, amakhiwane	Amahlathi amanzi nawomileyo kunye namahlathi acwecwe, kwiilathi ezikufuphi nemilambo nakwiilathi anamanzi angaphantsi komhlaba, kwiindawo ezinengca ezinemvela eninzi kunye ne-savanna, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,200m	i-tropical kunye ne-sub-tropical		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	umhlaba okhupha kakuhle amanzi kwiindawo ezinamanzi amaninzi phantsi komhlaba		ikhula ngokukhawuleza
<i>Ficus sur</i>	umthumbu, amakhiwane	Ecaleni kwemilambo, kwiilathi ngasemilanjani, kwihlathi elivulekileyo nasehlathini leengca, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,500m	10 - 35°C	800 - 1,800mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	umhlaba okhupha kakuhle amanzi kwiindawo ezinamanzi amaninzi phantsi komhlaba	iqabaka	50cm ngonyaka

Igama Lezityalo	Igama LesiXhosa	Ukwenzeka kwengingqi	Ubushushu	Imvula	Ukukhanya	Umlaba	Uvakalelo	Izinga lokukhula
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	Ukwenzeka kwengingqi Imithana, amahlathi avulekileyo kunye nehlathi, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-1,900m	15 - 25°C	800 - 1,800mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo, pH 6.5	iimeko ezibandayo	ikhula kancinci, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-2 (grafted), iminyaka emi-4 (seedlings)
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	IKaroo elomileyo, imithana yesanti eselunxwemeni, amahlathi angapheliyo asezingqongileyo kunye neengca ezinomthi.			isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti, umhlaba olinganiswe kakuhle, udongwe olunzima.		
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	Imithana eselunxwemeni kunye neKaroo, amahlathi angapheliyo anzulu, imida yamahlathi nezithwathwa, iinduli ezinamawa ezintabeni, ezikufutshane nemilambo nasemaphandleni emilanjani	10 - 35°C		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle		ikhula ngokukhawuleza, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-2
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenya	Amahlathi ngasemilanjani; kwiindawo eziphakamileyo ukuya kwi-1,400m	i-tropical kunye ne-sub-tropical		ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo, pH 6.5	iqabaka	1.5m ngonyaka
<i>Hoslundia opposita</i>		Ihlathi leSavanna, ngaphandle emilanjani, kwiindawo ezinehlathi, ukuya kutsho kwi-1,500m	i-tropical kunye ne-sub-tropical		ilanga eligcweleyo	umhlaba okhupha kakuhle amanzi		
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	Siqhele ukufumaneka kwiinduli ezivulekileyo, emahlathini aphakathi, kwiikloof ezimanzi nasemahlathini	i-tropical kunye ne-sub-tropical		isiqingatha somthunzi		ukumelana neqabaka	50cm ngonyaka, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-3
<i>Hyphaene coriacea</i>	ilala	Kufutshane nemilambo, kwiingxangxasi zesanti nakwiindunduma zolwandle	iindawo ezishushu, ezomileyo	250 - 1,500mm	ilanga eligcweleyo	ezahlukeneyo, pH 6.5		ikhula kancinci
<i>Milletia grandis</i>	umsimbeeti	Ufumaneka KwaZulu-Natal naseMpuma Koloni, kwaye uxhaphake ePondoland, kwiindawo ezifika kwi-600m		phezulu	ilanga, umthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle	ukumelana neqabaka	80 - 100cm ngonyaka
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>		Ufumaneka kwiindawo ezishushu nakumantla eMzantsi Afrika, kwiinduli ezinamatye, kwiinxweme zemilambo, emacaleni ehlati, nakumahlathi avulekileyo kunye ne-bushveld eyomileyo	15 - 25°C	phantsi	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo, pH 6.5	iqabaka	ikhula ngokukhawuleza, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-3
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	Lindonga zemilambo nemigxobhozo, ngamanye amaxesha kwiindawo ezinengca ezinamathafa aphezulu anamanzi, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-3,000m	15 - 35°C	500 - 5,000mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	ezahlukeneyo, umhlaba ogcwele amanzi okanye umhlaba ombi owomileyo pH 5 - 8		ukhula kwiminyaka emi-5
<i>Portulacaria afra</i>	igqwantsha	Siqhelele kwiinduli ezinamatye, iindawo ezinehlathi elincinci, amahlathi aqinileyo, i-bushveld, kunye nemilanjani eyomileyo	imozulu epholileyo	phantsi	ilanga eligcweleyo	ezahlukeneyo	ukumelana neqabaka	ikhula ngokukhawuleza
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga, ikhamanga	Iindawo yehlathi elingunaphakade kunye nehlathi lemthombo yolwandle		phezulu	ilanga eligcweleyo	ezahlukeneyo	ukumelana neqabaka	ikhula ngokukhawuleza
<i>Syzgium cordatum</i>	injomi, umdoni	Ufumaneka kumbindi nasemazantsi eAfrika kufuphi namanzi acocekileyo, ecaleni kwemilambo, emithaneni yemithi, nakwiinduli ezinamahlathi	10 - 35°C	600 - 1,500mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 5 - 8		1m ngonyaka
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	Ngasemilanjani, ekupheleni kwehlathi, kwiinduli ezomileyo ezinehlathi, nakwiindawo ezingafumani iliqhwa kakhulu, ukuya kutsho kwi-1,800m	kushushu	phantsi	ilanga eligcweleyo	umhlaba okhupha kakuhle amanzi		80cm ngonyaka, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-1
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkuhlu	Amahlathi ngasemilanjani nasemathafeni, ukuya kwi-1,800m	19 - 31°C	600 - 2,300mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	udongwe, umhlaba othambileyo, pH 6.5		1.5m ngonyaka, ukhula kwiminyaka emi-6
<i>Vangueria infausta</i>	amavilo	Kwiindawo ezineenduli zegusha, amahlathi amafutshane nakwiindawo ezivulekileyo zamahlathi, kananjalo kwiinduli ezenziwe ziingcongconi, kwiindawo ezinamatye nakwiindunduma zesanti, kwiindawo ezifika kwi-1,500m ngaphezu kolwandle	12 - 36°C	700 - 1,500mm	ilanga eligcweleyo; isiqingatha somthunzi	isanti elilinganiswe kakuhle, pH 5 - 8	ukumelana nembalela neqabaka	50cm ngonyaka
<i>Ziziphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	Kwiindawo ezahlukeneyo ezifana namahlathi, amazantsi avulekileyo, iinduli ezinemiqolomba, kunye namadlelo, ukuya kuthi ga kwi-2,000m ngaphezu komphakamo wolwandle	12 - 30°C	440 - 1,200mm	ilanga eligcweleyo	ezahlukeneyo		30cm ngonyaka

Itheyibhile A: Imilinganiselo yezityalo yokuwalasela ixesha elide

A1: Dumasi Creche

Uhlobo lwesityalo	Igama	Inani kwisiza N ngexesha lokutyala	Ujikelezo lwengcambu (cm) C ngexesha lokutyala	Ububanzi bentamo yengcambu (cm) RCD ngexesha lokutyala	Ubude (cm) H ngexesha lokutyala	N ngexesha lenyanga 3	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	N ngexesha lenyanga 6	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	7	2	0.64	22								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	4	6.5	2.07	71								
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	3	2.5	0.80	12								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	3	4.5	1.43	42								
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	imvutshwama	4	13	4.14	165								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	5	9	2.87	32								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	4	4	1.27	32								
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	42	3	0.96	34								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga	2	6	1.91	52								
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umthumba	2	3	0.96	26								
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	4	8	2.55	70								
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	1	6	1.91	96								
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	1	13	4.14	99								
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	1	9	2.87	103								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	2	6	1.91	50								
<i>Ficus sur</i>	amakhwane	1	5	1.59	66								
<i>Vangueria infausta</i>	amavilo	1	2.5	0.80	34								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	3	3	0.96	40								
Total		90											

A2: Mtolani Community Garden and Nursery

Uhlobo lwesityalo	Igama	Inani kwisiza N ngexesha lokutyala	Ujikelezo lwengcambu (cm) C ngexesha lokutyala	Ububanzi bentamo yengcambu (cm) RCD ngexesha lokutyala	Ubude (cm) H ngexesha lokutyala	N ngexesha lenyanga 3	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	N ngexesha lenyanga 6	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6
<i>Diospyros lycoides</i>	umbhongisa	11	4	1.27	73								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	8	3	0.96	32								
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	7	6	1.91	40								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	11	4.5	1.43	52								
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	mqokolo	4	4	1.27	53								
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>	Red milkwood	8	3.5	1.11	41								
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	16	2.5	0.80	37								
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkukhlu	16	3	0.96	29								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	2	4	1.27	43								
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	6	2	0.64	24								
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu	8	1.5	0.48	21								
<i>Englerophytum natalense</i>	umthongwane	1	5	1.59	70								
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	2	3	0.96	72								
<i>Syzygium cordatum</i>	injomi	16	2	0.64	25								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga	7	8	2.55	43								
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	2	3.5	1.11	78								
<i>Zizyphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	2	3	0.96	52								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	4	4	1.27	42								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	6	7	2.23	42								
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	2	12	3.82	156								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	1	6.5	2.07	97								
<i>Carissa bispinosa</i>	amathungula	2	2	0.64	23								
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	umthumbu	1	7	2.23	70								
Total		143											

A3: Baleni School

Uhlobo lwesityalo	Igama	Inani kwisiza N ngexesha lokutyala	Ujikelezo lwengcambu (cm) C ngexesha lokutyala	Ububanzi bentamo yengcambu (cm) RCD ngexesha lokutyala	Ubude (cm) H ngexesha lokutyala	N ngexesha lenyanga 3	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	N ngexesha lenyanga 6	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	28	5	1.59	61								
<i>Cordia caffra</i>		5	5	1.59	80								
<i>Mimusops zeyheri</i>	Red milkwood	9	6	1.91	36								
<i>Combretum erythrophyllum</i>	umdubu	1	5	1.59	85								
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	imvutshwama	3	14	4.46	242								
<i>Diospyros lycoides</i>	umbhongisa	9	4	1.27	75								
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	5	9	2.87	158								
<i>Grewia occidentalis</i>	ilalanyathi, umnqabaza	2	4	1.27	48								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	4	6.5	2.07	40.5								
<i>Ficus sur</i>	umthumbe	9	3	0.96	16								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	5	2	0.64	30								
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	mkuhlu	16	4	1.27	52								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	msinsi	1	5	1.59	60								
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	1	4	1.27	100								
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	18	1.5	0.48	16								
<i>Syzygium cordatum</i>	injomi	11	3	0.96	39								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	4	3.5	1.11	25								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skemanga	5	11	3.50	26.5								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	2	5	1.59	29.5								
<i>Albizia adianthifolia</i>	umgadankawu	3	1	0.32	14								
<i>Ficus natalensis</i>	amakhiwane	2	4	1.27	79								
<i>Dovyalis caffra</i>	mqokolo	2	3.5	1.11	35								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	1	6	1.91	28								
<i>Zizyphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	4	4	1.27	58								
<i>Carissa edulis</i>	amathungula	2	1	0.32	11								
<i>Hoslundia opposita</i>		6	1	0.32	20								
<i>Hyphaene coriacea</i>	ilala	2	17	5.41	47								
Total		160											

A4: Xolobeni School

Uhlobo lwesityalo	Igama	Inani kwisiza N ngexesha lokutyala	Ujikelezo lwengcambu (cm) C ngexesha lokutyala	Uubanzi bentamo yengcambu (cm) RCD ngexesha lokutyala	Ubude (cm) H ngexesha lokutyala	N ngexesha lenyanga 3	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 3	N ngexesha lenyanga 6	C (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	RCD (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6	H (cm) ngexesha lenyanga 6
<i>Berchemia zeyheri</i>	umnini	1	10	3.18	192								
<i>Trichilia emetica</i>	umkuhlu	2	4	1.27	67								
<i>Syzygium cordatum</i>	injomi	9	2.5	0.80	35								
<i>Harpephyllum caffrum</i>	umgwenye	28	5	1.59	61								
<i>Carissa macrocarpa</i>	amathungula	2	35	11.15	23								
<i>Portulacaria afra</i>	spekboom	3	4	1.27	10								
<i>Strelitzia nicolai</i>	skamanga	4	13	4.14	38								
<i>Diospyros whyteana</i>	umtenatane	2	4.5	1.43	26								
<i>Garcinia livingstonei</i>	amabimbi	4	4	1.27	28								
<i>Halleria lucida</i>	umbinza	1	3.5	1.11	86								
<i>Diospyros lycoides</i>	umbhongisa	1	4	1.27	112								
<i>Phoenix reclinata</i>	isundu	2	6	1.91	30								
<i>Canthium inerme</i>	imvutshwama	1	8	2.55	216								
<i>Hyperacanthus amoenus</i>	uthongothi	1	4	1.27	51								
<i>Tetradenia riparia</i>	iboza	1	5	1.59	31								
<i>Erythrina lysistemon</i>	umsinsi	2	6.5	2.07	77								
<i>Zizyphus mucronata</i>	umphafa	2	3	0.96	52								
Total		66											

IINDLELA ZOKUVELISA IZITYALO

Imbewu eyolashiweyo kakuhle

Ukukrwela imbewu

umtenatane
(*Diospyros whyteana*)

red milkwood
(*Mimusops zeyheri*)

Ukuyomisa ubusuku bonke

umqokolo
(*Dovyalis caffra*)

umpayi
(*Ficus natalensis*)

umthumbu
(*Ficus sur*)

Ukuyicwilisa ubusuku bonke

umdubu (*Combretum erythrophyllum*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

umsimbeeti
(*Milletia grandis*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

Ukuyicwilisa emanzini ashushu

umgadankawu
(*Albizia adianthifolia*)

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umbhongisa
(*Diospyros lycoides*)

umpfafa
(*Ziziphus mucronata*)

Imbewu egciniweyo

Imbewu egciniweyo

umgadankawu
(*Albizia adianthifolia*)

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umbinza
(*Halleria lucida*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

ilala (*Hyphaene coriacea*)

amavilo
(*Vangueria infausta*)

red milkwood
(*Mimusops zeyheri*)

Amasebe

lingcambu ezinamahlumela

ilala (*Hyphaene coriacea*)

isundu
(*Phoenix reclinata*)

skamanga
(*Strelitzia nicolai*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

amavilo
(*Vangueria infausta*)

Amasebe afumene ukwelashwa angeniswe kwihomoni yokukhuthaza ukukhula

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umqokolo
(*Dovyalis caffra*)

umsinsi
(*Erythrina lysistemon*)

umpayi
(*Ficus natalensis*)

umthumbu
(*Ficus sur*)

amabimbi
(*Garcinia livingstonei*)

umbinza
(*Halleria lucida*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

orange bird-berry
(*Hoslundia opposita*)

uthongothi
(*Hyperacanthus amoenus*)

igqwanitsha
(*Portulacaria afra*)

iboza
(*Tetradenia riparia*)

amavilo
(*Vangueria infausta*)

Amasebe amakhulu anquyiweyo nawomisiweyo emthunzini

umsinsi (*Erythrina lysistemon*)

umbinza
(*Halleria lucida*)

umgwenya
(*Harpephyllum caffrum*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

Ukwaleka komoya ukusuka kwisebe

amathungula
(*Carissa spp*)

umthumbu
(*Ficus sur*)

umkuhlu
(*Trichilia emetica*)

Ukuphuhlisa izakhono zoluntu lwasekuhlaleni kwi-Agroforestry yesiNtu kummandla wase-Amadiba eMpuma Mpondoland